

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

FOUR STAGES OF NUCLEAR WINTER MODELING

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Abstract

Forecasts of a nuclear winter that can result from a large-scale nuclear war were obtained simultaneously and independently by scientists of the USSR and the USA in 1983-1985. The main factor causing a Nuclear winter is the powerful fires that have arisen as a result of the bombing of large cities, which have turned into "fire tornadoes". The magnitude of the temperature drop at different points of the earth's surface ranges from -5 to -50 degrees. The forecasts received by Soviet scientists of the USSR in 1988 are presented. for the case of the consequences of a large-scale nuclear war for an isolated human population and obtained by US scientists for the regional war between India and Pakistan in 2008-2022. The simulation results showed that the consequences of this regional conflict can have significant global consequences.

Keywords: Nuclear winter forecasts, nuclear arsenal, forced optimization, mathematical models of global climate and biosphere processes, high spatial resolution of the model, food security.

This year marks the 40th anniversary of the research of the "Nuclear Winter" in 1983-1985. However, the danger of a nuclear winter has not decreased by now, but has increased. It has been supplemented by new countries with nuclear weapons and a new danger – the possibility of using them in regional wars has appeared. As the calculations of the participants of the nuclear winter have shown, these weapons can have not only a significant regional negative impact, but also global consequences. Therefore, the importance of conducting research on the consequences of the use of nuclear weapons is still far from over. In this article, the author describes four stages of modeling the "Nuclear Winter" – up to 2022.

The idea of a Nuclear winter was expressed by K. Sagan after P. Krutzen and J. Birks in 1982 drew attention to the fact that in World War II, as a result of strong bombing by American aircraft of large German cities, when large-scale fires occurred and large updrafts formed - "fire storms" [3]. The effect of the fact that as a result of nuclear bombing of large cities, giant masses of smoke and soot will fly into the atmosphere, which, spreading over vast distances, will block solar radiation, and the temperature of the atmosphere will decrease significantly, was called "Nuclear winter".

First forecasts of a Nuclear winter that will result from a large-scale nuclear war were obtained simultaneously and independently by scientists of the USSR and the USA in 1983-1985. The main factor causing a Nuclear winter is the powerful fires that have arisen as a result of the bombing of large cities, which have turned into "fire tornadoes". The magnitude of the temperature drop at different points of the earth's surface ranges from 5 to 50 degrees.

At the beginning of 1983, a group of US climate scientists gathered together, they agreed on a joint scenario that determines how many products of large-scale

nuclear war will be sprayed in the atmosphere, to what height, what particle sizes, etc. Among them was the Soviet scientist Vladimir Alexandrov. By autumn, the calculations were completed.

By the same time, A.M. Tarko had developed an ecological model – a model of the biogeochemical cycle of carbon dioxide in the biosphere with high spatial partitioning [6]. Both models were the only ones in the country on which long-term global forecasts could be calculated, taking into account the spatial distribution of land and ocean.

In September 1983, N.N. Moiseev, V.V. Alexandrov and A.M. Tarko attended the symposium "Coevolution of Man and the Biosphere" held in Helsinki by the Institut de la Vie, and there V.V. Alexandrov firstly reported the results of the Nuclear winter. Calculations have shown that the drop in the temperature of the Earth's atmosphere as a result of the overlap of a huge amount of soot from solar radiation should be about 20-50° C. In the same place, A.M. Tarko reported the first results of possible ecological and demographic consequences of the scenario implementation.

Almost at this time, similar climatic and environmental results were obtained and reported by US scientists. A significant result of US and Russian scientists was that the country that starts a nuclear war will inevitably will be destroyed from its own or someone else's nuclear strikes.

After the appearance of forecasts of Nuclear winter in developed countries, information about was spread rapidly: newspapers were full of information and photos of participants in the work on nuclear winter, scientific and popular books were published.

The organization of publications on nuclear winter was taken over by the international organization SCOPE – the Scientific Committee on Environmental

Problems. It gave scientists the opportunity to get together at international workshops, to attract the missing specialists. SCOPE published two volumes "Consequences of Nuclear War" and a popular book. The first volume was devoted to climatic consequences [4], the second – ecological and agricultural [5]. Both volumes were soon translated into Russian. By the end of 1985 the main materials on Nuclear winter forecasts were published, both international and national [1 - 6].

Unfortunately, in the midst of the event, Vladimir Alexandrov, who received the results of climatic consequences in the USSR, disappeared without a trace, being invited to report to a conference of mayors of non-nuclear cities in Spain. From Cordoba, where the conference was held, he flew to Madrid, feeling unwell. The staff of the Soviet embassy put him in a hotel, he left it for a walk and ... disappeared. The international measures taken to find him did not lead to anything.

At the second stage of work on the Nuclear winter, forecasts of the possibility of medium-term survival of the population after a large-scale nuclear war were obtained. The main assumption of the model of scientists of the USSR, carried out in 1988 [9], is the hypothesis that a large-scale nuclear war will destroy almost the entire population, there will survive isolated popula-

tions. A nuclear war will destroy industry, throw agriculture of the surviving population to primitive medieval technology.

The possibility of survival of isolated agricultural autarkies deprived of external energy inflows, as well as machines and advanced agricultural technologies is investigated. Survivors cluster in areas of less dense pre-war settlement. There are no external connections, sources of food, energy, clothing, etc. Although the Nuclear winter is over, the air temperature remains low, which depresses agroecosystems. Radioactive pollution of the environment annually leads to the death of a part of the population, but the accumulation of genetic cargo does not occur. In the basic version of the model, it is assumed that there are no epidemics, epizootics, natural disasters and outbreaks of agricultural pests.

The model is a system of difference equations with variable coefficients and allows the introduction of control. A model of a human population with an age structure of three homogeneous cohorts is considered: "children" aged 0 to 15 years, "adult" members of the reproductive age population from 15 to 50 years, and "elderly", older than 50 years. The difference equation of reproduction of the number of livestock is also recorded, taking into account the current livestock, its fertility, mortality and slaughter rate. The scheme of causal relationships of the model is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Diagram of causal relationships of the human population model after a large-scale nuclear war

Then implemented on a computer, a territory was selected, enclosed between 56°N and 60°N and 52°E and 57°E., corresponding to the Nizhny Novgorod region of the USSR.

Computing experiments have shown that the system has one single equilibrium state, this is the trivial state. That is, the population either survives for some time or dies. The model is ultimately linear and is not designed to describe long-term, about a hundred years, processes.

In another series of experiments, it was shown that for a given initial population size, there is a critical

value of animal fertility, below which the animal population dies, then people also die. That is, the possibility of survival of the population strongly depends on the initial conditions.

When analyzing the effects of post-nuclear radiation on people, the most dangerous phenomena were identified. The first years after a nuclear war are the most dangerous for survival.

The study of the influence of variations to weather and other fluctuations of agricultural crops has shown that they only worsen population dynamics: the greater the amplitude of fluctuations, the greater the damage to the population.

Two types of optimizations were performed: the search for the largest population size at the boundary of the time interval under consideration or the maximum value of the minimum number over the entire time interval. The advantage of these forced optimizations was that they allowed us to establish the best options from, in any case, negative consequences. These do not mean that the population itself could be able to fix the situation, but shows only the utmost possibilities. The conducted study of the influence of various types of optimizations of economic management allowed improving only quantitative indicators, without affecting the qualitative trends of growth or extinction.

In general, looking by all the variants of model experiments, the existence of mankind after a nuclear war will take place in the most difficult conditions of food shortage. The average daily energy consumption will be 2,100 kcal by the end of the fifth decade and in the future will not exceed 2000-2100 kcal, which is below the level that actually exists for people engaged in physical labor and living in the least developed developing countries.

The next stage of work was carried out in this century jointly by few scientists who made forecasts for the Nuclear winter in the USA and in the USSR in 1983-1985. It was completed by 2007 and consisted in taking into account the new circumstances with nuclear weapons in the world that had developed by that time with the use of the latest climate models for calculations [7].

By then, the world's nuclear arsenal had been reduced by three times, but the number of nuclear-weapon states had increased. The authors used the latest model of the general circulation of the atmosphere and ocean, and the simulation was carried out for a 10-year period. Nuclear winter scenarios began to be calculated not by the total power of nuclear weapons, but by the total amount of nuclear aerosol (soot and smoke)

released into the atmosphere - 50 and 150 tons of soot, these values reproduce most of the global arsenal. The reaction to the 150 Tg scenario can be described as a Nuclear winter, which leads to global catastrophic consequences.

The changes obtained during the simulation turned out to be longer than previously assumed, since the new model was able to reproduce the rise of nuclear aerosols into the middle and upper stratosphere, ensuring its long stay there. Such an impact of nuclear weapons would also have devastating consequences for the planet.

The atmospheric model was linked to a complete model of the general ocean circulation with calculated sea ice, which allows the ocean to react quickly at the surface and on an annual scale in the deeper layers of the ocean. The atmospheric part of the model had a resolution of $4^\circ 5^\circ$ in latitude and longitude with 23 vertical layers extending to the height calculated on the model by 80 km.

The authors carried out calculations of 10-year experiments with 150 Tg and 50 Tg of soot that reached the upper layers of the troposphere (300-150 mbar) within one week, and covered all cells of the adopted grid in the United States and Russia.

According to the scenario, 150 Tg would be thrown out when using the entire existing global nuclear arsenal with a capacity of 5,000 Mt, about 95% of which is in the arsenals of the United States and Russia, and 50 Tg would be thrown out when using 1/3 of the existing nuclear arsenal. Fig. 2 shows a map of the decrease in atmospheric temperature under the selected scenario. Cooling is most noticeable on land, but significant cooling is also observed over the oceans. The warming over Antarctica in year 0 is for a small area, is part of normal winter interannual variability, and is not significant.

Fig. 2. Surface air temperature changes for the 150 Tg case averaged for June, July, and August of the year of smoke injection and the next year. Effects are largest over land, but there is substantial cooling over oceans, too.

A global freezing and stay there for more than a year. In Ukraine, for example, average surface temperature of 7°C to 8°C persists for years, it stays below freezing for more than two years. After a decade the cooling is still 4°C. This would have agricultural implications. Comparison is a result of the cooling of the Earth's surface, the last ice age 18,000 years ago was about 5°C. In this evapotranspiration is reduced and the global hydrological would be a climate change unprecedented in speed and cycle is weakened.

The resulting global precipitation is reduced and after the year is 45%. Cooling of more than 20°C occurs precipitation change for the Northern Hemisphere summer over large areas of North America and of more than 30°C one year after the smoke.

The current stage of the work was carried out in 2008-2022 USA, it continues at the present time [11, 12]. After the discovery of the Nuclear winter effect in a large-scale war, the danger of a global nuclear war was supplemented by the possibility of regional wars. Important possible consequences of such wars, in addition to climatic ones, are agricultural production and demographic changes. These works for the case of a regional war between India and Pakistan were carried out by US scientists in 2008-2022. Separated by more than 20 years of work on the large-scale war of 1983-1985 and the scale of events, these forecasts turned out to be similar in a number of consequences. The simulation results showed that the consequences of this regional conflict can also have significant global consequences.

Modeling was carried out with several basic scenarios, which are conditionally divided by the total amount of soot that flew into the high layers of the atmosphere as a result of fires after the exchange of nuclear strikes – 5, 16, 27, 37 and 47 Tg. The latter value corresponds to the scenario when the outbreak of war occurs in 2025 and the entire arsenal available to the countries, according to the forecast, is used – 250 warheads each. According to Stockholm international peace research institute (SIPRI), in 2022 India had 160 warheads, Pakistan had 165 warheads [8].

The climate Model of the Earth Community System (CESM) is used in the work. This model includes the atmosphere, land, ocean, and sea ice. Both the atmosphere and the land have a horizontal resolution of 1.9°×2.5°, and the ocean has a horizontal resolution of 1°. An atmospheric model is a climate model of the entire atmospheric community. The land model is a model with a carbon-nitrogen cycle. CESM output data with a resolution of 1 and 3 hours, including air temperature, precipitation, specific humidity, long-wave radiation and solar radiation (direct and scattered radiation), are

used for use in the model of agrocenoses, including crops.

The Whole Atmosphere Community (WACCM) climate model as an atmospheric component was also used. WACCM is a "high—precision" chemical-climatic model with an upper boundary located at an altitude of about 140 km. It was used to be able to simulate the physical and chemical consequences of the injection and lifting of soot to great heights in the atmosphere.

According to the scenarios used, the war begins either with a terrorist attack on one of the countries, or has random causes. Each scenario assumes a nuclear war lasting one week. The active factors are the decrease in atmospheric temperature caused by the action of products released into the high layers of the atmosphere as a result of fires from nuclear strikes, most of which are released from huge fires in large cities.

During the development of the scenarios, attention was paid to the difference in the composition of the firing products. Accordingly, estimates of smoke from different sources were taken into account. The measured fraction can vary widely, from nearly 90% to less than a few percent, depending on the material of the burning products. The average soot emission factor was adopted, taking into account the range of fuel types and combustion conditions expected in nuclear attack scenarios.

It was taken into account that the violation of the Earth's climate limits the production of terrestrial and aquatic food. Scenarios for crop production, animal husbandry and fishing were used. The total number of food calories available in each country in the post-war period was predicted.

Climate, crop production and fisheries models were used to assess the effects of six scenarios of carbon black release into the stratosphere, predicting the total amount of food calories available in each country in the post-war period after the consumption of stored products. Soot emissions exceeding 5 Tg lead to massive food shortages, and livestock and water feed production will not be able to compensate for the decline in crop yields in almost all countries. Adaptive measures, such as reducing food waste, will have a limited impact on increasing the amount of calories available.

According to calculations, more than 2 billion people in the world may die as a result of a nuclear war between India and Pakistan. The climate consequences in this case will be not only regional, but also global. The general simulation results for all scenarios are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Number of warheads used for urban targets, yield, direct losses from bomb explosions and the total number of people who are at risk of death due to hunger, for scenarios

Soot (Tg)	Number of weapons (warheads)	Yield (kt)	Number of direct fatalities	Number of people left without food at the end of 2 years
5	100	15	27 000 000	255 000 000
16	250	15	52 000 000	926 000 000
27	250	50	97 000 000	1 426 000 000
37	250	100	127 000 000	2 081 000 000
47	500	100	164 000 000	2 512 000 000

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food calories available in each country in the post-war period was predicted.

Climate impacts will last for about a decade, but will peak in the first few years (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Decrease in surface temperature (deg. C, vertical axis) of monthly climatic variables in agricultural crops in different years from the beginning of the war (horizontal axis) of the simulated nuclear war, depending on the mass of soot and dust ejected (Tg). For comparison, during the last ice age 20,000 years ago, the average temperature of the earth's surface was about 5°C lower than at present

The cooling caused by nuclear wars leads to temperature restrictions for crops, which leads to a delay in physiological maturity and additional cold stress. The reduction in caloric intake as a result of agriculture and consumption of marine fish demonstrates regional differences, with the strongest percentage reduction occurring in the high latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere. In the case of India and Pakistan, many regions become unsuitable for agriculture for several years. For example, in the case of 27 Tg in the middle and high latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere, there is a decrease in the caloric content of plant products by more than 50%, along with a reduction in fish catch by 20-30%.

If a war ever breaks out between India and Pakistan, as is assumed here, between 50 and 125 million people could die in these countries alone, which would be a regional catastrophe. In addition, serious short-term climate changes, in which temperatures will drop to values not seen on Earth since the middle of the last ice age, will be caused by smoke from burning cities, a global catastrophe threatening food production worldwide and mass starvation, as well as serious disruption of natural ecosystems.

The average global production of food (calories) from simulated crops will decrease by 7% in 1-5 years after the war, even under the most minimal scenario - 5 Tg of soot and up to 50% under the scenario of 47 Tg. The changes will lead to a catastrophic failure in world food markets, since even a 7% reduction in the global harvest compared to the control model would exceed the largest anomaly ever recorded by the FAO.

Caloric intake in the post-war period implies that extreme regional reductions could be overcome to some extent through trade, but the equal distribution of food around the world would probably become a serious problem.

In conclusion, reduced illumination, global cooling and likely trade restrictions after nuclear wars would be a global catastrophe for food security. The

negative impact of climate change on the overall production of crop production, as a rule, cannot be compensated by animal husbandry and aquatic food.

References:

1. Aleksandrov V.V., Stenchikov G.L. On the modelling of the climatic consequences of the nuclear war. // Moscow: Computer Center, USSR Acad. Sci. - 1983.- p. 10.
2. Alexandrov G.A., Armand A.D., Belotelov N.V., Pasekov V.P., Logofet D.O., Svirezhev Yu.M., Tarko A.M. et al. Mathematical models of ecosystems. Ecological and demographic consequences of nuclear war. M., Nauka, 1986, 176 p. (in Russian).
3. Crutzen P.J., Birks J.W. The Atmosphere after a Nuclear War: Twilight at Noon. // AMBIO. A Journal of the Human Environment. 1982. V. 11, p. 114-125.
4. Environmental Consequences of Nuclear War. Physical and Atmospheric Effects. SCOPE 28. – Eds.: Pittock A. B., Ackerman T. P., Crutzen P. J., MacCracken M. C., Shapiro C. S., Turco R. P. – Wiley, U.K., 1985. – v. 1, 359 pp.
5. Environmental Consequences of Nuclear War. Ecological and Agricultural Effects. SCOPE 28. – Eds.: Harwell M. A., Hutchinson T. C. – Wiley, U.K., 1985, v. 2, 523 pp.
6. Moiseev N. N., Alexandrov V. V., Tarko A. M. Man and the biosphere. Experience of system analysis and experiments with models. Moscow: Nauka. - 1985. - 272 p. (in Russian).
7. Robock A., Oman L. & Stenchikov G. L. Nuclear winter revisited with a modern climate model and current nuclear arsenals: still catastrophic consequences. J. Geophys. Res. 112, D13107, 2007.
8. Stockholm international peace research institute. [electronic resource]. <https://www.sipri.org/yearbook/2022>. (accessed: 03/11/2023)
9. Svirezhev Yu.M., Gaidukov O.Yu., Tarko A.M., Yatsalo B.I. Analysis of the consequences of nuclear war: agricultural production and demography. Messages on applied mathematics. Computing Center

of the USSR Academy of Sciences. Moscow. 1988, p. 30. (in Russian).

10. Tarko A.M. Modeling the consequences of nuclear war as a strategic deterrent to potential aggressors. // Strategic priorities. International Scientific and Analytical journal. No. 4 (16), Moscow, 2017 pp. 34-51.

11. Toon O.B., Bardeen C.G., Robock A., Xia L., Kristensen L., McKinzie M., Peterson R.J., Harrison C.S., Lovenduski N.S., Turco R.P. Rapid expansion of

nuclear arsenals by Pakistan and India portends regional and global catastrophe. *Sci. Adv.* 5, eaay5478, 2019.

12. Xia, L., A. Robock, K. Scherrer, C. Harrison, B.L. Bodirsky, I. Weindl, J. Jägermeyr, C. Bardeen, O.B. Toon, and R. Heneghan, 2022: Global food insecurity and famine from reduced crop, marine fishery and livestock production due to climate disruption from nuclear war soot injection. *Nat. Food*, 3, no. 8, 586-596, doi:10.1038/s43016-022-00573-0.